

Space-time window reconstruction inside finite volume simulations

- Reducing storage for scientific simulations

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Abstract

The scope of this work is to reduce the storage requirements for scientific simulation data by reconstructing space-time windows defined inside the solution frame, with increased or lower mesh resolutions.

The price for handling large datasets of scientific simulations is very restrictive for most computational science and engineering users. It is necessary to develop new approaches on the handling of simulation data and provide solutions for visualization on commodity computers.

The mainstream approaches from the literature can be grouped according to Table 1.

1	Remote access to dataware centers [1]	Centralised, hard to replicate, vulnerable location
2	Specialized (parallel) filesystems [2]	Equipment-dependant, immobile
3	Databases [3]	Not really adapted to time-varying multidimensional data
4	Floating Point Compression [4,5,6,7]	Not practical for very large output or phenomena that locally appear as random variances
5	Distributed cache prefetchers [8]	Network-dependant, suitable for LAN of commodity computers

Table 1 – Mainstream Approaches from Literature

Rows 4 and 5 in Table 1 present the implementations that make use of commodity hardware, and thus have great potential for unlocking the chains which bind computational scientists and engineers to expensive and limited resources. However the user is still bounded to high-speed network or Internet connections, and has limited improvements on the storage and transport capabilities.

We have successfully experimented with the extraction of window-defined boundary conditions on specific time intervals, using the OpenFOAM case format, and we have used the extracted information to reconstruct the space-time subdomain contained within the configured window box. In this case, we have successfully reconstructed the velocity vector fields from the *pitzDaily* test case, according to user-defined space and time subdomains. The space and time subdomain is defined as a rectangular cuboid of interest.

The extracted points are interpolated such that meshes with a different resolution can be used during the reconstruction process. The accuracy of the reconstruction, the time required to recompute the values and the gain in storage requirements are evaluated and discussed. Different interpolation techniques and various density levels for the extracted points, are also taken into account.

In Figure 1 (a) the velocity field from the *pitzDaily* test case is presented at the final timestamp 1000. The user-defined rectangular cuboid is a bounding box of coordinates (0.075 -0.02 -0.0005) (0.15 0.01 0.0005). The boundary conditions required for reconstructing the contained subdomain are extracted and stored. The stored data is then interpolated for a new submesh resolution and the same *simpleFoam* solver is used to reconstruct the contained, missing subfield, as obtained in Figure 1 (b).

The procedure can be applied to any number of timestamps, which, in turn, can be reconstructed in parallel when the necessary hardware is available.

The slight color scale difference in Figures 1 (a) and (b) shows that the reconstruction has been done in different, unconnected case directories and the accuracy of the reconstruction is taken into account and discussed.

This is work in progress, which has been studied in different contexts, and is yet to be published. By only saving the necessary boundary conditions and the original geometry, the storage requirements are drastically reduced on behalf of the computational power needed to reconstruct the subfields.

Key words: space-time window, subdomain reconstruction, scientific data handling

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